

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

Türkiye Country Report: An Analysis of Diamond Open Access Publishing in Türkiye

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Note to readers

Due to the earthquake in Türkiye, it was decided to postpone the surveying of possible Turkish respondents. The survey was distributed to Turkish respondents during autumn 2023. Unfortunately, it turned out that the response rate was too low to allow for a meaningful discussion based on the few responses.

We decided to ask our Turkish contacts to prepare a report. As it is not based on survey data, it has another “look and feel” than the other country reports. We find it useful to publish it as a separate report, so that Türkiye is also covered with a comprehensive report, enabling the interested reader to gain insight into how things are and how things work in Türkiye.

As of June 6th 2025, Türkiye ranks 10th in DOAJ's list of countries as to the number of journals listed there, with 571. Of these journals, 406 let the authors retain all rights, and 535 are diamond journals. This indicates that institutional publishing is a major part of Turkish OA publishing. Türkiye has 207 institutional publishers in DOAJ by the end of 2024 (Crawford (2025a); (Crawford, 2025b)), 200 of which publish diamond journals.

Introduction

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This report has been prepared primarily through a collaborative effort by a dedicated team within TÜBİTAK ULAKBİM.

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Table of Contents

Note to readers	1
Introduction	2
Authors	2
Authors and contributors	2
Table of Contents	3
Acronyms, abbreviations etc.	5
1. Executive Summary DIAMAS Türkiye Country Report: An Analysis of Diamond Open Access Publishing in Türkiye	7
2. Diamond Publishing Landscape in Türkiye	12
2.1 Institutional Framework and Engagement	12
2.2 Open Access Development and Policies	13
2.3 Funding Models and Sustainability	17
2.4 Collaboration and Infrastructure	18
2.5 Challenges and Opportunities	21
3. Operational Aspects of IPSPs.....	23
3.1 Staffing and Human Resources	23
3.2 Technological Infrastructure	24
3.3 Editorial Workflow and Quality Assurance	25
3.4 Services Offered	27
3.5 Funding and Financial Management.....	28
3.6 Collaboration and Networking	29
4. Academic Output and Accessibility	31
4.1 Types and Scope of Academic Outputs	31
4.2 Accessibility and Open Access Distribution	34
4.3 Quality Assurance and Impact Metrics	35
4.4 Language Diversity and Multilingual Publishing	37
4.5 Barriers to Access and Strategies for Improvement.....	39
5. Language Diversity and Inclusion	40
5.1 Language Policies in Turkish Publishing	40
5.2 Multilingual Publishing Practices	40

5.3 Inclusivity and Accessibility.....	43
5.4 Impact of Language Diversity on Scholarly Communication	44
5.5 Supporting Language Diversity.....	44
Conclusion	45
6. Engagement and Best Practices	46
6.1 Community Engagement and Collaboration.....	47
6.2 Adherence to International Publishing Standards	48
6.3 Best Practices in Editorial and Peer Review Processes	50
6.4 Open Science and Data Sharing	51
6.5 Capacity Building and Professional Development.....	51
Conclusion	52
7. Conclusion and Recommendations	55
Recommendations	57
Final Words	58
Appendices.....	59
References.....	59
List of Tables.....	59
List of figures	59

Acronyms, abbreviations etc.

Acronym	Explanation
ANKOS	Anatolian University Libraries Consortium
APC	Article Processing Charges
CERN	Conseil européen pour la recherche nucléaire
DOAJ	Directory of Open Access Journals
ERA	European Research Area
TR Index	Türkiye's official indexing service for scholarly publications
TÜBİTAK	The Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye
UDS	ULAKBİM Dergi Sistemleri (ULAKBİM Journal System)
ULAKBİM	National Academic Network and Information Centre
YÖK	The Council of Higher Education
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
COPE	Committee on Publication Ethics
WoS	Web of Science

1. Executive Summary

DIAMAS Türkiye Country Report: An Analysis of Diamond Open Access Publishing in Türkiye

The DIAMAS Türkiye Country Report presents a comprehensive analysis of the current state of Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing in Türkiye. As part of the global DIAMAS initiative, the report focuses specifically on Diamond OA journals that do not charge article processing fees, aiming to enhance the infrastructure and practices of open access publishing within the European Research Area (ERA).

Founded in 1963 with the mission to advance science and technology, conduct research, and support Turkish researchers, the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TÜBİTAK) is the principal organization responsible for supporting and directing scientific and technological research in Türkiye. TÜBİTAK operates independently and is governed by a Governing Board composed of distinguished academics from universities, industry, and research institutions.

The analysis of responses to the DIAMAS survey highlights that TÜBİTAK's practices related to Diamond Open Access services do not yet fully align with the desired standards. Due to insufficient survey responses, this report has been prepared primarily through a collaborative effort by a dedicated team within TÜBİTAK ULAKBİM.

In the Turkish academic landscape, there are three primary motivations for publishing among academics and universities: academic promotion, incentives, and performance evaluation. Academics face pressure to publish to advance their careers, while universities strive to enhance academic productivity to improve their rankings. Academic incentives play a critical role in shaping researchers' publishing preferences. In academic appointment and promotion processes, candidates are required to accumulate points by publishing in journals indexed by WoS, Scopus, or TR Index. Articles published in high-impact journals yield higher scores, with the intention of encouraging researchers to produce quality publications. Universities that achieve high

rankings gain national and international recognition, becoming magnets for top-tier academics and students. Quality publications not only enhance a university's prestige but also contribute to the academic community through the content produced by university presses, reflecting positively on the institution's overall success.

Open access publishing plays a significant role in alleviating the pressures placed on authors, as it enables wider dissemination of research and supports academic incentives and promotion opportunities. Furthermore, it enhances universities' visibility in national and international rankings. Open access journals increase the visibility of authors, thereby attracting more citations and contributing to academic success. Supporting Diamond Open Access publishing represents a strategic approach to meeting academic achievement criteria. The management and publication of Diamond Open Access journals are facilitated in Türkiye through DergiPark, a platform provided by TÜBİTAK for the digital publication of academic journals. Currently, TÜBİTAK publishes 11 Diamond Open Access academic journals across various disciplines, adhering to open access principles and serving the academic community. Approximately 800 articles are published annually in these journals. Most of the publications indexed in TR Index, where scientific criteria are rigorously applied, are also open access. Further details regarding DergiPark, TR Index, and TÜBİTAK Academic Journals can be found in subsequent sections of this report.

TÜBİTAK's International Scientific Publications Incentive Program (UBYT) provides financial support to authors publishing in journals indexed by WoS. This program incentivizes Turkish researchers to publish more articles in high-visibility, high-impact journals (Demir, 2018). Notably, in this program, open access publications receive higher incentive scores compared to non-open access publications. Aligning the incentive policies of open access journals with these measures not only supports authors but also ensures that scientific knowledge reaches broader audiences.

Key Findings:

- 1. Institutional Engagement:** The Diamond Open Access (OA) model is supported by projects that contribute to the development of open access standards across Europe, notably DIAMAS (Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models). These projects encourage the adoption of Diamond OA publishing by focusing on important issues such as sustainability, quality and collaboration (<https://diamasproject.eu/>). In Türkiye, the majority of Diamond OA publications are managed by higher education institutions, reflecting a strong academic commitment to open access. The DergiPark platform, supported by TÜBİTAK, plays an important role in open access publishing in Türkiye; 95% of the approximately 2,500 journals in DergiPark publish in accordance with the Diamond OA model. Türkiye data on DergiPark and TR Index will be discussed in the following sections of the report.
- 2. Funding and Sustainability:** While the global movement toward OA publishing has gained momentum, funding remains a primary concern for many Turkish publishers. The report highlights the need for diversified funding models to support the long-term sustainability of OA publications, moving beyond traditional subscription models and author processing charges.
- 3. Open Access Policies and Practices:** Türkiye has made significant progress in adopting Open Access (OA) practices, particularly through the mandatory requirement for OA publication of publicly funded research by many institutions. However, there remains room for improvement in national OA strategies to further support and promote Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing. In order to guide open science initiatives, develop institutional and national policies on open science and open access, and align with the European Union's legislative framework and programs, the "TÜBİTAK ULAKBİM National Open Science Committee" was established in 2015. This committee worked towards ensuring that TÜBİTAK have an Open Science Policy. As a result of the committee's efforts, the TÜBİTAK Open Science Policy was published in 2019. For more details, you

can access the policy here: [TÜBİTAK Open Science Policy Document](#) (Turkey, 2019).

As part of its Open Science initiatives, TÜBİTAK ULAKBİM is involved in various projects such as Aperta Türkiye Open Archive for managing research data, Harman Türkiye Academic Archive as a national harvester of institutional repositories, the Research Data Education Portal, and the Open Course Platform. These projects are designed to facilitate access to research outputs and promote open data and knowledge sharing in Türkiye, further enhancing the country's commitment to open science.

4. **Technological and Operational Infrastructure:** The technological infrastructure supporting OA publishing in Türkiye varies widely among institutions. While some have adopted advanced platforms and editorial systems (DergiPark, OJS etc.), others rely on more basic setups. Collaborative efforts and knowledge sharing within the academic community could enhance the publishing infrastructure.
5. **Language and Multicultural Inclusion:** The report highlights the significance of language diversity in Open Access (OA) publications in Türkiye, emphasizing that multilingual publishing practices are crucial for engaging the local academic community while also enhancing the visibility of Turkish research on the global stage. By supporting a wider range of languages, academic publishing can become more accessible and inclusive. However, the report also points out a disadvantage for non-English languages in Türkiye, as global indices primarily rely on English, which creates challenges for non-English publications. Despite this, some journals in the TR Index publish in various languages, though they are in the minority. The distribution of articles in DergiPark by language reveals that 74% are in Turkish, 24% in English, and about 1% in other languages, including Arabic, German, Russian, French, Kazakh, Kurdish, Persian, Azerbaijani, Italian, and other languages. In TR Index, 25% of accepted journals are published exclusively in English, 6% in Turkish, and 69% are multilingual, including Turkish, English, German, and other languages.

Table 1 Language distribution of articles in DergiPark

Language of Articles	Number of Articles	Percentage
Turkish	544,624	74.58%
English	179,567	24.59%
Arabic	2,179	0.30%
German	1,260	0.17%
Russian	896	0.12%
French	672	0.09%
Kazakh	438	0.06%
Kurdish	349	0.05%
Persian (Farsi)	94	0.01%
Azerbaijani	67	0.01%
Italian	19	0.003%

6. **International Collaboration and Standards:** Turkish publishers are increasingly adopting international standards and best practices in academic publishing, which is essential for enhancing the quality, visibility, and impact of Open Access (OA) publications in Türkiye. The Entrepreneurship Index created by TUBITAK and the Research Universities Ranking created by the Council of Higher Education (YÖK), create pressure on institutions to improve the quality of national publications. This pressure encourages journals to focus on improving their quality indicators, such as their impact factor (Q-values). Additionally, the growing recognition of the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) in Türkiye is also promoting open access publishing. However, research and studies in this area have not yet reached the level needed to fully support and advance this movement.

2. Diamond Publishing Landscape in Türkiye

Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing landscape in Türkiye reflects a complex ecosystem shaped by the country's rich academic traditions, diverse linguistic heritage, and evolving digital infrastructure. This section provides an overview of the Diamond OA landscape in Türkiye, highlighting key characteristics, players, and trends.

2.1 Institutional Framework and Engagement

Higher education institutions (HEIs), research centres and scientific societies in Türkiye play important roles in the development of Diamond OA publishing. These institutions host and manage academic journals. They also support the scholarly communication process through services such as editorial management, peer review and dissemination. Concrete steps to be taken in the field of open science and open access in Türkiye have been determined by the Council of Higher Education (YÖK) and these are as follows:

- Establishing a commission under the chairmanship of a rector or vice-rector responsible for open science and open access studies at universities and organising meetings with the participation of academics to raise awareness on this issue,
- Amendment to the Regulation on Academic Incentives for publishing in open access journals and producing open course materials,
- Ensuring the participation of the relevant personnel of universities in the training meetings organised by YÖK,
- Reporting the studies carried out by universities and the number of publications in academic archives on a semi-annual basis in a method and format determined by YÖK, and launching similar initiatives ([Council of Higher Education Open Access Page](#)).

These steps demonstrate a strong commitment of Turkish higher education institutions to open science and knowledge sharing. Many Turkish universities have established their own publishing units or platforms to disseminate research findings to a wider audience. These efforts are enabling the creation of a vibrant publishing environment with contributions from academic societies and state-funded research organisations. For example, there are 1,507 journals from 182 universities on the DergiPark platform. The distribution of the number of journals on DergiPark by university is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Distribution of universities based on the number of journals they publish

2.2 Open Access Development and Policies

Global trends, regional initiatives, and national policies have significantly shaped the course of Open Access (OA) development in Türkiye. Beyond the general goal of increasing the visibility and accessibility of Turkish academic publications, demands from funding agencies and academic institutions have emerged as critical drivers for the transition to OA practices. Although this country report focuses on Diamond open access processes in Türkiye, the subject is not limited to Diamond Open Access; it is also important to highlight initiatives carried out in the field of open access in general. In particular, TÜBİTAK, one of the leading advocates of the OA movement in Türkiye, has played a significant role in promoting this transformation by negotiating and implementing transformative agreements. For example, TÜBİTAK's "read and publish" agreements with two world-renowned publishers have provided significant opportunities for Turkish authors to publish their work in Open Access formats.

A prominent example is the agreement with Wiley, which spans from 2023 to 2025, offering an annual quota of approximately 1,500 OA article publications. As illustrated in

Figure 2, an analysis of Türkiye's three-year OA publication trends reveals a marked increase in articles published in Gold OA journals over the past two years. This notable growth can be largely attributed to the transformative agreement initiated in 2023, which has facilitated broader adoption of OA publishing practices and expanded the reach of Turkish research within the global academic community.

Figure 2 Number of hybrid and gold open access articles affiliated with institutions in Türkiye and published by Wiley from 2022 to 2024

The transformative agreement with Springer, spanning the years 2024 to 2026, marks another significant milestone in Türkiye's Open Access (OA) publishing landscape. This agreement facilitates an annual quota of approximately 2,500 OA article publications, reflecting a strategic effort to further integrate Turkish research into the global scholarly ecosystem.

As demonstrated in Figure 3, an analysis of Türkiye's five-year OA publication trends indicates a notable increase in the number of articles published in hybrid OA journals. This upward trajectory is likely a direct outcome of the 2024 agreement, which has incentivized and supported researchers in transitioning to hybrid OA models. By enabling broader dissemination of scholarly work, this initiative not only enhances the visibility of Turkish academia but also aligns with global best practices in OA publishing, fostering a more inclusive and accessible academic environment.

Figure 3 Number of open access articles from institutions in Türkiye published in Springer hybrid journals (2020-2024)

Collaborative efforts in Open Access (OA) publishing play an important role in advancing Türkiye's integration into global scientific initiatives. A notable example is the Sponsorship Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics (SCOAP3), an international OA project coordinated by CERN. This consortium centralizes the financial contributions of member countries and institutions to high energy physics (HEP) journals, ensuring that HEP articles are transformed into freely accessible resources for participating countries. Türkiye has been an active member of SCOAP3 since 2014, strongly demonstrating its commitment to global scientific collaboration and open dissemination of knowledge. In addition, SCOAP3's pilot application "SCOAP3 for Books", which aims to make high energy physics books open access, was launched in 2019 and is also supported by TÜBİTAK ULAKBİM. Thanks to the collaboration between SCOAP3 and ULAKBİM, both the visibility and the number of open access articles published in the field of high energy physics in our country have increased significantly.

At the national level, the Anatolian University Libraries Consortium (ANKOS) has significantly contributed to OA initiatives. Since the establishment of the Open Access and Institutional Archives (AEKA) working group in 2006, ANKOS has spearheaded efforts to build the foundation for OA archives across Türkiye. This group provides

guidance, fosters collaboration, and disseminates best practices through training and support, thereby strengthening institutional OA infrastructures.

ANKOS has also negotiated transformative OA agreements with several prestigious publishers, including Cambridge University Press (CUP), the American Chemical Society (ACS), Oxford University Press (OUP), the British Medical Journal (BMJ), the Institute of Physics (IOP), the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM), and SAGE Publishing. These agreements cover authors affiliated with ANKOS member institutions, facilitating broader access to OA publishing opportunities and aligning with global publishing standards.

Recent years have seen a growing emphasis on developing national strategies to institutionalize OA practices. TÜBİTAK, a key driver of Türkiye's scientific advancement, has made significant strides in this area. Its Open Science Policy mandates that all publications resulting from TÜBİTAK-funded projects be made openly accessible. To this end, TÜBİTAK supports the Green Open Access model through its APERTA Open Archive platform. Researchers are required to upload peer-reviewed articles to the archive immediately upon acceptance or, at the latest, within six months for STEM fields and 12 months for social sciences and humanities. The policy ensures that article metadata are publicly accessible, machine-readable, and discoverable from the moment of upload, thereby promoting transparency and the rapid dissemination of research findings.

Additionally, TÜBİTAK strongly advocates for the development of Research Data Management Plans to facilitate the open sharing of research data associated with funded publications. Compliance with the Open Science Policy is a critical factor in evaluating researchers' performance and eligibility for future funding. TÜBİTAK's 1001 support program now requires mandatory Data Management Plans, further institutionalizing OA practices and fostering a culture of openness in research.

These initiatives reflect Türkiye's dedication to aligning its scientific output with international standards. By fostering transparency, accessibility, and collaboration,

Türkiye is strengthening its integration into the global research community and positioning itself as an active contributor to the advancement of open science.

2.3 Funding Models and Sustainability

Funding remains a cornerstone of sustaining and enhancing Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing, directly influencing the quality, accessibility, and longevity of academic journals. In Türkiye, the funding landscape for OA journals is diverse, encompassing institutional contributions, grants from scholarly societies, and government support. However, the sustainability of Diamond OA journals is fraught with challenges that parallel those faced globally, including the necessity for stable financial backing, efficient cost management, and the cultivation of long-term funding models.

This report delves into the funding strategies adopted by Turkish publishers, evaluating their implications for the resilience and viability of OA journals in the national context. An exemplary initiative in this regard is DergiPark, a government-funded platform that provides a robust technological infrastructure for open access publishing. Since its inception in 2013, DergiPark has expanded from supporting 100 journals to hosting more than 2,500 journals today, with approximately 690,000 registered users. This remarkable growth underscores its role in standardizing academic publishing practices across Türkiye while aligning them with international norms. By substantially reducing costs for universities and other institutions, DergiPark has democratized access to scholarly publishing, enabling registered users to participate in editorial, peer-review, and authorship processes. Moreover, it fosters capacity-building through both face-to-face and online training programs, empowering registered users and ensuring adherence to rigorous publication standards.

Despite these significant advancements, the Turkish OA ecosystem requires additional resources to enhance both the quantity and quality of its scholarly output. While Türkiye has made strides by negotiating transformative OA agreements with major publishers such as Wiley and Springer, funding remains a critical bottleneck. The agreements have contributed to a noticeable increase in the number of OA publications; however, the

allocation of financial resources to OA remains disproportionately low. Currently, less than 5% of the national academic publishing budget is directed toward open access initiatives. To remain competitive in the global academic publishing landscape, Türkiye must prioritize increased investment in OA, enabling the further development of its infrastructure, the adoption of innovative publishing practices, and the enhancement of journal quality.

By addressing these funding gaps and reinforcing institutional support mechanisms, Türkiye can solidify its position as a leader in Diamond OA publishing. Such efforts will not only bolster the sustainability of its academic journals but also enhance the visibility and impact of Turkish research within the international scholarly community, fostering a culture of openness and collaboration that aligns with global trends in science and education.

2.4 Collaboration and Infrastructure

Collaboration among academic institutions, libraries, and publishers serves as a cornerstone for strengthening the Diamond Open Access (OA) ecosystem in Türkiye. Such partnerships and networks facilitate the sharing of resources, expertise, and best practices, thereby enhancing the efficiency, diversity, and impact of OA publishing. By fostering cooperative efforts, stakeholders can address shared challenges and create a sustainable, high-quality publishing landscape that aligns with international standards.

A key initiative in promoting quality and diversity in Turkish academic publishing is the TR Index, which emphasizes an international and gender-balanced approach to editorial board structures. These principles aim to ensure objectivity and inclusivity in scholarly publications. The TR Index Journal Evaluation Criteria outline several essential aspects for journal evaluation:

Editorial Board Quality:

Editorial boards must comprise members with significant expertise and experience in their fields. The inclusion of independent and international members is critical to ensuring diverse perspectives in editorial decision-making.

Gender Balance and Diversity:

Journals are encouraged to maintain gender-balanced editorial boards to foster inclusivity and equitable representation in the publishing process.

Publication Accuracy:

High standards for language, spelling, and grammar accuracy are required. In addition, proper typesetting and formatting of materials are essential for maintaining professionalism and readability.

International Representation:

Editorial, advisory, and reviewer boards are expected to include experts from various countries and regions, ensuring a global perspective in the journal's content and operations.

Independence and Integrity:

Editorial decisions must be made independently of external influences to preserve academic integrity and prevent biases.

In line with these principles, the TR Index mandates that journals ensure diversity among institutions and authors represented in their publications. Quotas are established to prevent overrepresentation from the same institution or authors, thus promoting a more inclusive and diverse academic publishing environment.

The technological infrastructure supporting OA journals is another critical factor for their success. Platforms like Open Journal Systems (OJS) play a pivotal role in managing the complexities of the academic publishing process, including peer review, article tracking, and metadata compatibility. Initially, DergiPark operated through the OJS platform, benefiting from its robust capabilities and adherence to international standards. However, the rapid expansion of DergiPark, which now hosts nearly 2,500 journals and engages approximately 690,000 registered users, necessitated a more scalable solution.

In response, the ULAKBIM Journal System (UDS) was developed in 2017. As a locally designed system, UDS retains the international standards upheld by OJS while addressing the increasing demands of a growing user base. Key features of UDS include:

Peer Review Management:

UDS supports processes such as anonymous and double-blind peer review, ensuring transparency and integrity.

Article Tracking and Publication:

Authors and editors can track article statuses throughout the publication process, enhancing workflow efficiency and communication.

OA Policies:

The system ensures that publications are managed in alignment with open access standards, reinforcing accessibility and compliance.

Metadata Compatibility:

Articles submitted through UDS meet metadata requirements for international indexing and databases, broadening the reach and discoverability of Turkish academic publications.

Moreover, UDS continues to evolve in response to user feedback, incorporating enhancements to meet the dynamic needs of researchers, editors, and institutions. By combining a commitment to global standards with localized solutions, Türkiye demonstrates its dedication to advancing the Diamond OA ecosystem and supporting the dissemination of high-quality, impactful research on both national and international scales.

2.5 Challenges and Opportunities

The development of open access(OA) publishing in Türkiye presents both challenges and opportunities. While issues such as funding sustainability, language diversity, and international visibility pose obstacles, the country's strategic position, academic resources, and the global shift toward open science offer significant growth potential.

Key Challenges

Financial Constraints

Limited budgets and high costs associated with article processing charges (APCs) and platform memberships hinder the adoption of OA publishing in Türkiye. Sustainable funding mechanisms are urgently needed to address these financial burdens.

Awareness and Education

Many researchers and institutions lack understanding of OA benefits and processes. Targeted education and outreach are critical for increasing participation in OA initiatives.

Infrastructure and Technology

Establishing and maintaining OA repositories that meet international standards requires investment in robust technological systems and expertise.

Policy and Support

While national initiatives like the "Open Access Strategy of Türkiye" exist, further action from institutions like YÖK and TÜBİTAK is needed to align policies with global standards and ensure long-term sustainability.

Language and Accessibility

Enhancing access to Turkish OA resources and translating research for global audiences are essential for fostering local engagement and international recognition.

International Visibility

Increasing the presence of Turkish research in global indexes and overcoming language barriers are vital to achieving greater academic impact.

Cultural Norms

Shifting perceptions about OA's value in career progression and journal prestige is necessary to encourage wider adoption.

Opportunities

Türkiye's proactive efforts, such as participating in European OA platforms and implementing national strategies, demonstrate strong potential. The global emphasis on open science, combined with Türkiye's geographic position and academic resources, provides a solid foundation for advancing OA publishing. Investments in education, infrastructure, and policy reforms can transform challenges into opportunities, enabling Türkiye to establish a sustainable and globally impactful OA ecosystem.

3. Operational Aspects of IPSPs

This section explores the operational dimensions of Institutional Publishers and Service Providers (IPSPs) in Türkiye, focusing on staffing, infrastructure, and services. These elements are critical in ensuring the efficiency, quality, and sustainability of Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing.

3.1 Staffing and Human Resources

The cornerstone of any publishing activity is the human resources that carry it out. The human resource structure of Institutional Publishing Support Providers (IPSPs) in Türkiye varies significantly from institution to institution. While leading universities and research centres have professional teams dedicated specifically to academic publishing and editorial processes, in smaller universities such tasks are often undertaken by faculty members, volunteers or part-time staff.

However, this difference is not limited to staff size. While some large institutions have staff specialized in publishing ethics, digital publishing technologies, open access policies and indexing processes, in others these competencies are concentrated in a single person. In institutions with a lack of human resources, serious difficulties are experienced in the institutionalization, sustainability and quality assurance of processes. Moreover, the fact that the editorial work carried out within the scope of IPSP is often carried out as an “additional task” in addition to the main academic obligations of academic staff may negatively affect both labour productivity and publication quality in the long run. Therefore, increasing human resource capacity and professionalizing editorial processes are critical for the development of institutional publishing activities.

This chapter analyses the human resource structure of IPSPs in Türkiye and discusses common roles and challenges in recruiting staff for Diamond OA publications. In particular, it is important for library staff to be knowledgeable about and interested in open access (OA). In addition, it should be ensured that relevant staff are trained to work in open access publishing and follow world standards. In this process, it is also of great

importance to provide financial support to publishing organisations through comprehensive policies.

3.2 Technological Infrastructure

The technological backbone supporting IPSP operations in Türkiye encompasses a range of tools and platforms, from manuscript submission systems to full-fledged publishing and distribution platforms. The adoption of standardized systems like the Open Journal Systems (OJS) is increasing, facilitating more streamlined and transparent editorial processes. DergiPark has a major role to play in ensuring the adoption of these systems. This subsection delves into the current state of technological infrastructure among Turkish IPSPs, including software use, digital archiving, and access facilitation. DergiPark has been providing infrastructure and hosting services to Türkiye-based, open access, peer-reviewed academic journals with the local and national software under the name OJS between 2013 and 2016, and ULAKBİM Journal Systems (UDS) since 2017. The UDS interface was made mobile-compatible in 2021, and the mobile application was launched in 2023. DergiPark platform is also designed for use by the visually impaired. 95% of the 2,500 journals in the system are Diamond Open Access journals. In recent years, DergiPark has been reviewing its service policy due to the fact that some journals have started to charge article processing fees to authors in order to publish higher quality articles.

DergiPark has sponsorship agreement with CrossRef. In DergiPark platform, the articles meeting DergiPark criteria are provided with a DOI, free of charge. Among the 2,538 journals in the platform, approximately 1,500 journals receive DOI through DergiPark. The rest is expected to improve their quality and adopt certain best practices to start receiving DOIs.

DergiPark and TR Index are integrated with EBSCO to increase the visibility of the articles.

3.3 Editorial Workflow and Quality Assurance

The DIAMAS reports highlight variations in academic publishing processes across countries, particularly in quality assurance and editorial workflows. Their research underscores the importance of implementing standardized practices in institutional publishing, fostering open science, and ensuring financial sustainability.

DIAMAS reports also illuminate the use of tools and automated mechanisms to enhance both technical and content-related editorial processes, providing valuable insights for improving global publishing practices.

The findings of DIAMAS reports underscore the importance of similar quality assessment mechanisms for platforms like DergiPark in Türkiye. Aligning closely with DIAMAS recommendations, DergiPark offers an article management system that adheres to international standards. Since 2017, DergiPark has been operating on ULAKBİM Dergi Sistemleri (UDS), a domestically developed software by TÜBİTAK ULAKBİM with over 690,000 users, the platform provides automated notifications, records every step of the publication process, and generates detailed statistics such as acceptance/rejection rates and processing times for journals. These functionalities—enabled by the robust infrastructure of UDS—not only enhance user experience but also significantly contribute to the transparency, scalability, and efficiency of academic publishing in Türkiye. To further enhance publishing quality, DergiPark is introducing two key features. First, by restructuring the Journal Board system, board member information will shift from manual entry to a user-invitation model. This change will ensure that board members are informed of their affiliations and allow for the presentation of statistics related to their contributions. Second, the Publisher Page feature, set to launch in 2025, will provide comprehensive and up-to-date information about journal publishers, including contact details.

Türkiye's academic publishing ecosystem includes approximately 3,500 academic journals, with 1,190 indexed in TR Index, 220 in WoS. DergiPark hosts 2,500 open access journals, 95% of which follow the diamond open access model. However, only 6% of

these diamond OA journals are indexed in global databases like WoS and Scopus. Notably, 85% of articles in TR Index and 75% of all articles in Türkiye are published as open access, with DergiPark ensuring compliance with international standards.

TR Index plays a critical role in auditing journals, regardless of whether they are hosted on DergiPark or other platforms. By enforcing adherence to general publishing and ethical principles, including the guidelines of the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), TR Index enhances the quality and integrity of academic publishing in Türkiye. It also conducts citation analyses and plans to classify journals by their impact factors in the future, further contributing to their competitiveness on global platforms.

The strategic alignment of TR Index, DergiPark, and international frameworks like DIAMAS illustrates Türkiye’s commitment to advancing its academic publishing ecosystem. This approach not only improves the quality and visibility of Turkish research but also strengthens its position within the global scholarly community.

Figure 4 Annual distribution of publications indexed in TR by access type (2014-2024)

The processes of the articles for the years 2022-2024 are ongoing. Journals indexed in TR Index are reviewed every year, and articles in journals that meet the journal evaluation criteria are indexed. The acceptance rate has decreased in recent years. In addition, the numbers continue to be updated as the evaluation and article data indexing processes of journals with applications continue.

3.4 Services Offered

DergiPark plays a pivotal role in Türkiye's academic publishing ecosystem by providing a robust platform for managing and publishing scholarly journals, particularly those following the Diamond Open Access (OA) model. DergiPark provides a comprehensive journal management system (UDS) designed to support the growing number of journals and users. The UDS platform offers significant flexibility, allowing journals to customize editorial workflows in line with their specific publication policies. Key features include automatic similarity analysis tools, integration with metadata repositories, and cross-platform compatibility, enhancing the efficiency and reliability of the publishing process.

Beyond submission and publication services, DergiPark ensures the long-term digital preservation of articles through integration with national repositories. This capability safeguards the accessibility and archiving of scholarly content over time. Additionally, its support for multilingual publications enables Turkish research to reach a global audience, contributing to the international dissemination of knowledge. As a central hub for diamond OA journals, DergiPark facilitates free access to research without imposing financial burdens on authors, thereby promoting equity in academic publishing.

TR Index, Türkiye's official indexing service for scholarly publications, complements DergiPark by offering critical services such as journal indexing, citation tracking, and annual quality assessments. These functions ensure that indexed journals adhere to rigorous editorial and publication standards, bolstering their visibility and credibility. TR Index also provides valuable insights into impact factors and citation metrics, while offering data on the full-text availability of indexed articles.

Promoting open access is a key priority for TR Index, with approximately 85% of its indexed articles available without subscription barriers. An increasing proportion of these publications is indexed in international databases such as Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus, integrating Türkiye's academic output into the global scholarly ecosystem. By enhancing the discoverability and competitiveness of Turkish journals, TR Index plays a vital role in amplifying the international impact of Turkish research.

These platforms collectively embody Türkiye's strategic commitment to advancing open access publishing while maintaining academic integrity and quality control. They align with global trends in academic publishing by fostering greater accessibility, visibility, and collaboration. Furthermore, partnerships with national and international platforms such as WoS and Scopus strengthen the reach and impact of Turkish journals, positioning Türkiye as an active participant in the global academic community. Through these concerted efforts, DergiPark and TR Index not only enhance the stature of Turkish research but also contribute to the broader goal of equitable and sustainable scholarly communication.

3.5 Funding and Financial Management

The financial sustainability of Diamond Open Access (OA) initiatives represents a critical operational consideration. Unlike traditional publishing models, Diamond OA relies on funding sources other than article processing charges (APCs), resulting in diverse financial management strategies among Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) in Türkiye. This section explores these strategies, focusing on how IPSPs balance operational costs through institutional support, grants, and donations.

Aligned with its commitment to open access and scholarly communication, the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TÜBİTAK) publishes 11 Diamond OA academic journals. This model reflects TÜBİTAK's dedication to facilitating access to academic research without imposing financial burdens on authors. Both TÜBİTAK Academic Journals and DergiPark exemplify this approach by offering DOI registration to authors and editors free of charge, with all expenses covered by public

funds. This framework ensures accessibility and sustainability of open access publishing while upholding equitable academic dissemination.

As the volume of academic publications in Türkiye increases, there has been a parallel rise in the commercialization of scholarly publishing. In response, the Council of Higher Education (YÖK) introduced specific restrictions on APC-based OA journals in its academic promotion criteria. New evaluation standards were implemented for tenure applications, and publications not meeting these criteria were excluded from consideration. These measures aim to address the commercialization of academic publishing while encouraging transparency and ethical practices.

However, the absence of national policies explicitly promoting Diamond OA highlights a critical gap. There is a pressing need to foster collaborative frameworks involving multiple institutions to support and expand Diamond OA initiatives. Such collaborations could establish a more sustainable and unified approach to funding, aligning with global best practices in open access publishing.

Through its public funding model and emphasis on Diamond OA, Türkiye demonstrates its commitment to making academic research accessible and sustainable. Nevertheless, strengthening institutional collaborations and adopting national-level policies could further enhance the impact and sustainability of these initiatives, ensuring that Diamond OA continues to thrive within the evolving landscape of scholarly communication.

3.6 Collaboration and Networking

Collaboration among Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) offers opportunities for resource sharing, collective bargaining, and the establishment of unified standards, all of which can significantly advance the Diamond Open Access (OA) ecosystem. This subsection examines the extent of cooperation and networking among Turkish IPSPs, including their partnerships with libraries, consortia, and international

organizations, and assesses how these collaborations influence operational efficiencies and enhance publishing quality.

Key initiatives fostering collaboration include training sessions and webinars conducted by TR Index, which aim to equip publishers, librarians, and authors with the knowledge and tools necessary to adopt open access practices, adhere to publishing standards, and utilize advanced technologies. Similarly, the ANKOSLink meetings – annual conference of publishers and librarians – provide a dynamic forum for discussing innovations and trends in academic publishing, offering valuable insights and support to institutions navigating the rapidly evolving landscape of scholarly communication.

These efforts are complemented by targeted training programs designed for editors, publishers, authors, and researchers. Covering diverse topics such as editorial workflows, peer review processes, ethical publishing practices, and effective academic writing, these programs aim to elevate the overall quality of academic publishing in Türkiye. By fostering an environment of continuous learning and professional development, these initiatives contribute to a more robust and interconnected publishing ecosystem.

Despite these advancements, the absence of a national policy explicitly promoting inter-institutional cooperation in academic publishing remains a significant limitation. While existing initiatives demonstrate the potential for collaboration, the lack of coordinated, nationwide strategies restricts the scalability and impact of open access efforts. Establishing a comprehensive national framework to encourage inter-institutional partnerships could unlock the full potential of Diamond OA in Türkiye, enabling more cohesive and impactful open access initiatives.

By expanding collaborative networks and fostering a culture of shared knowledge and resources, Türkiye's academic publishing community has the opportunity to strengthen its position within the global scholarly communication landscape. Such efforts would not only enhance operational efficiencies but also ensure the sustainability and international competitiveness of Turkish academic journals.

4. Academic Output and Accessibility

This section examines the nature and scope of academic outputs within the Turkish Diamond Open Access (OA) ecosystem, alongside the accessibility of these materials to the broader academic community and the public. Emphasizing the pivotal role of these elements, the discussion underlines the importance of quantitative and qualitative measures in enhancing scholarly communication.

4.1 Types and Scope of Academic Outputs

Turkish IPSPs contribute to various academic outputs, encompassing peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, monographs, and more. This diversity reflects the rich scholarly landscape of Türkiye and caters to a broad academic audience.

The number of academic journals, articles published and registered users in DergiPark, which is an example of IPSP in Türkiye, is shown in the graphs below.

Figure 5 Annual number of journals indexed in DergiPark (2013-2024)

When DergiPark was launched in 2014, one of its primary objectives was to ensure that electronic journals in Türkiye were published in accordance with international standards and with clean metadata. To support this goal, all journal applications were initially accepted, and the journals were monitored over the following years. In 2019, a comprehensive review was conducted to identify journals that had not published their scheduled issues, and these journals were subsequently removed from the platform. Based on the analysis of these discontinued journals, the application criteria for new journals were tightened. The decrease in the number of journals in 2019 can be attributed to this process, despite the overall annual growth trend in journal numbers. However, since access to the articles from the discontinued journals has been maintained, there has been no decline in the total number of available articles.

Figure 6 Annual number of articles displayed in DergiPark (2014–2024)

Figure 7 Annual number of registered users on DergiPark (2014–2024)

Registered users on DergiPark include not only authors, reviewers, and editors, but also readers who use the platform's follow feature to access scholarly content.

Additionally, articles and final reports of funded projects are indexed by TR Index. The proceedings database module will be indexing national conference proceedings similar to Web of Science (WoS) Conference Proceedings Citation Index (CPCI) in 2025. In the Proceedings Database, a database containing bibliographic data, metadata and full-text proceedings of the papers presented at scientific meetings in Türkiye will be established.

Creating a database for books and monographs to improve quality and facilitate long-term preservation is on the roadmap for future.

4.2 Accessibility and Open Access Distribution

The core principle of Diamond Open Access (OA) lies not only in the elimination of publication fees but also in ensuring unrestricted access to scholarly works. This subsection explores the accessibility of Turkish academic outputs, focusing on their reach and impact both domestically and internationally. Key areas of discussion include the mechanisms facilitating access, the visibility of Turkish research on global platforms, and adherence to international accessibility standards.

Platforms such as DergiPark and TR Index play a pivotal role in enhancing the discoverability of Turkish academic works. Through their integration with widely used services such as EBSCOHost and Google Scholar, these platforms significantly expand the audience for Turkish research. For instance, Google Analytics data from January to December 2024 indicates an impressive 28,024,822 visits to the TR Index, alongside 1,842,062 logins and 13,026,660 searches conducted via EBSCOHost. These metrics underscore the global reach of Turkish academic outputs. Additionally, Crossref registration and the widespread adoption of DOIs contribute to the efficient distribution and citation of content, further enhancing its impact.

DergiPark's user-friendly infrastructure also includes a mobile application available on both Android and iOS platforms, facilitating access across diverse devices. Moreover, the platform incorporates features designed to support the visually impaired, although it currently lacks formal accessibility certification. This highlights an area for improvement in aligning with global accessibility standards.

Analysing user engagement provides critical insights into the effectiveness of these platforms. However, usage data for DergiPark and TR Index is collected from various sources in a fragmented manner, complicating comprehensive analysis. Annual evaluations of the data guide the development of strategies aimed at improving the platforms' performance and outreach. According to Google Analytics, in 2024 approximately 8% of the 3,600,000 visitors to TR Index were from abroad. Similarly, from May 2023 to May 2024, 22% of the 23,000,000 visitors to DergiPark originated from outside Türkiye, reflecting its growing international audience. Notably, approximately

20% of all access to the DergiPark platform was routed through Google Scholar, highlighting its importance as a gateway to Turkish academic content.

These platforms exemplify Türkiye's commitment to increasing the global visibility and accessibility of its scholarly outputs. While significant progress has been made, further efforts to achieve comprehensive data integration and formal accessibility certifications could bolster their effectiveness. Strengthening these aspects would not only enhance the platforms' international competitiveness but also align them more closely with global best practices in open access publishing.

Figure 8 Browser language preferences of DergiPark users based on Google Analytics data (January-December 2024)

4.3 Quality Assurance and Impact Metrics

The credibility and impact of academic outputs are gauged through rigorous quality assurance processes and various impact metrics. In the criteria announced at, there is a clause stating that "Attention should be paid to the diversity of institutions and authors in the articles published in the journal."

[TR Index journal evaluation criteria](#) can be defined under the following main headings.

1. Journals should be in compliance with research and publication ethics, journal ethics policies should be established (presence and evaluation processes of articles of editors and journal boards, transparency, etc.), information about permission should be included in studies requiring ethics committee permission.
2. Compliance of the referee evaluation system with the processes, referee impartiality, diversity, competence and contribution, adequacy, effectiveness, content quality of referee reports and evaluations, etc.
3. Quality, competence, contribution, independence, publication rigour (in terms of language and spelling), product rigour (in terms of typesetting, etc.), international and geographical representation of the journal (authors, referees, advisory and editorial board).
4. Compliance with spelling rules, accuracy and conformity of article sources to standards, quality of article title, abstract and keywords

TR Index, which has been carried out by ULAKBİM since 1993 to increase the quality and international visibility of national scientific publishing and to provide access to national content has been serving as a National Citation Index. The journals to be included in the index are meticulously evaluated in line with the TR Index Journal Evaluation Criteria, which are compatible with international criteria and updated every year (<https://trdizin.gov.tr/en/criteria/>). As of July 2024, more than 576,000 articles are indexed in TR Index, and the full text of approximately 500,000 articles is accessible.

In order to trigger the innovation and entrepreneurship activities of universities and to measure their performance in this field, the Entrepreneurial and Innovative University Index was prepared for the first time in Türkiye by TÜBİTAK in 2012. Within the scope of the Index, the 50 most entrepreneurial and innovative universities are ranked according to 23 indicators based on the following criteria: “scientific and technological research competence”, “intellectual property pool”, “cooperation and interaction” and “economic and social contribution”. Each year, the index is resorted and announced.

The "[University Monitoring and Evaluation General Report](#)" has been released by YÖK since 2019). The report is prepared and published by YÖK every year through analysing the relevant data in order to support the functions of universities while also evaluating their performances in terms of academic publishing.

In addition, University Ranking by Academic Performance (URAP) is a non-profit organization which was established at the Informatics Institute of Middle East Technical University (METU) in 2009. The main objective of URAP is to develop a ranking system for the world universities based on academic performance indicators that reflect the quality and the quantity of their scholarly publications. In line with this objective URAP has been releasing the World Ranking of Higher Education Institutions annually since 2010, and Field Rankings since 2011. URAP 2023-2024 Türkiye ranking tables can be accessed at <https://newtr.urapcenter.org/>.

4.4 Language Diversity and Multilingual Publishing

Language is a pivotal element in the accessibility and dissemination of academic knowledge. In Türkiye, a nation celebrated for its rich linguistic and cultural diversity, Diamond Open Access (OA) initiatives face the dual challenge of ensuring local relevance while achieving international visibility. The interplay of language diversity and multilingual publishing is essential for fostering inclusivity in scholarly communication, particularly in a region where linguistic pluralism reflects the broader societal fabric.

The distribution of articles published via DergiPark offers a snapshot of this dynamic: 72% are in Turkish, 24% in English, and an additional 4% in other languages such as Kyrgyz, Dutch, Russian, German, Arabic, French, Kurdish, Azerbaijani, Italian, Chinese, Uzbek, Bulgarian, Persian, Urdu, Georgian, Spanish, and Albanian. This linguistic breadth highlights the potential of Türkiye's academic ecosystem to embrace multilingualism while addressing the distinct needs of its diverse audiences.

Figure 9 Language distribution of published articles in DergiPark

While Turkish remains the dominant language in academic publishing, the inclusion of languages that are minorities in Türkiye, such as Kurdish, Arabic or Kyrgyz, demonstrates Türkiye's efforts to reflect its linguistic diversity. These initiatives point to the potential of multilingual academic publishing to increase access to research, strengthen intercultural dialogue and support the intellectual contributions of different language communities.

However, expanding the scope of TR Index to include more journals publishing in English and other languages could significantly enhance Türkiye's academic visibility on a global scale. Such an expansion would not only elevate the international standing of Turkish research but also facilitate greater integration into global scholarly networks.

Multilingualism in academic publishing, while advantageous, presents considerable challenges. Funding constraints and technological barriers are among the most pressing issues. Ensuring the availability of standardized multilingual metadata is critical for facilitating effective indexing and retrieval of research articles across languages. Additionally, the translation of research outputs into multiple languages requires substantial institutional and governmental support, as it is both resource- and labour-intensive.

Despite these challenges, Türkiye has made strides toward inclusivity in academic publishing. For instance, open access repositories are increasingly designed to support multiple languages, while collaborations among researchers from different linguistic backgrounds promote cross-cultural academic exchanges. Advocacy for language rights in academia further emphasizes the importance of cultural pluralism in scholarly communication.

Promoting language diversity in an open access environment not only bridges linguistic divides but also strengthens Türkiye's contributions to global research. By integrating diverse languages into its academic publishing framework, Türkiye embraces a more inclusive and globally engaged scholarly landscape. Initiatives aimed at fostering multilingualism reflect a broader commitment to academic inclusivity, global collaboration, and the democratization of knowledge, ensuring accessibility for all, regardless of language.

In conclusion, the integration of linguistic diversity into Diamond OA initiatives holds transformative potential. By overcoming barriers and leveraging opportunities, Türkiye can position itself as a leader in fostering multilingual scholarly communication, enriching both its domestic academic discourse and its influence within the global research community.

4.5 Barriers to Access and Strategies for Improvement

Despite the strides in OA publishing, barriers to access still exist, ranging from technological challenges to linguistic and socioeconomic factors. This part identifies the main obstacles to accessing Turkish academic outputs. It discusses the strategies implemented or proposed by IPSPs and other stakeholders to overcome these obstacles, ensuring broader and more equitable access to scholarly information.

5. Language Diversity and Inclusion

This section addresses the critical themes of language diversity and inclusion within the Turkish Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing framework. The diversity of languages in academic publishing fosters greater inclusivity and enhances the global dissemination and understanding of scholarly works.

5.1 Language Policies in Turkish Publishing

Türkiye's rich linguistic heritage and cultural diversity deeply influence the language policies adopted in academic publishing. Traditionally, Turkish has been the dominant language of academic publishing. However, in recent years, efforts have increased to include minority languages in academic publishing. These developments reveal a desire to better reflect Türkiye's multilingual structure and cultural diversity in the academic field.

Platforms such as DergiPark are diversifying their publishing policies in order to support this multilingualism. For example, some journals accept articles not only in Turkish but also in languages such as English, French and Arabic. This approach encourages academic contributions from different language communities and democratizes access to research.

Language policies in academic publishing in Türkiye play an important role in reflecting the country's linguistic diversity and encouraging multilingual academic communication. The development and implementation of these policies have the potential to create a more inclusive and accessible environment for both the national and international academic communities.

5.2 Multilingual Publishing Practices

In the context of multilingual publishing in Türkiye, TR Index and DergiPark serve as cornerstone platforms that support the dissemination of scholarly outputs in multiple languages, reflecting the country's linguistic and cultural diversity. Both platforms play

a critical role in fostering inclusivity and ensuring that academic works are accessible to a wide array of audiences, both locally and internationally.

TR Index, Türkiye's national academic database, primarily indexes journals publishing in Turkish, thus maintaining the country's scholarly identity. However, its scope also extends to journals that publish in English and other regional languages such as Arabic, Kurdish, Kazakh, and Azerbaijani. This diversity reflects a commitment to promoting linguistic inclusivity while enabling local research to gain international visibility.

Table 2 Number of journals in TR Index according to publication language

English	1,345
Turkish	1,083
German	101
French	87
Arabic	82
Russian	33
Azerbaijani	3
Kurdish	3
Italian	2
Kazakh	2

The multilingual capacity of TR Index enhances its role as a bridge between local academic traditions and global research standards. By adhering to rigorous indexing criteria, TR Index ensures that the quality of indexed journals meets international benchmarks, regardless of the publication language. Additionally, expanding TR Index's scope to include more journals publishing in English and other widely spoken languages could further strengthen the global reach of Turkish research outputs.

DergiPark, a comprehensive open-access journal hosting platform managed by TÜBİTAK, plays a pivotal role in supporting multilingual publishing efforts in Türkiye. Currently, 72% of the articles published on DergiPark are in Turkish, 24% in English, and

a smaller percentage in other languages, including Arabic, Kurdish, Persian, Azerbaijani, and French. This linguistic variety reflects the platform's adaptability and inclusivity.

DergiPark's integration with global indexing systems such as Google Scholar, EBSCOHost, and Crossref enhances the visibility of its hosted journals. The widespread adoption of DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) ensures that articles, regardless of their language, are easily accessible and citable in the global academic ecosystem.

Furthermore, DergiPark offers technological features to support accessibility for diverse user groups, including a mobile application available for Android and iOS platforms and tools designed for the visually impaired. However, the platform currently lacks formal accessibility certification, which presents an opportunity for further development.

Both TR Index and DergiPark demonstrate the potential of multilingual publishing in fostering a more inclusive academic environment. However, challenges remain:

- Translating articles and maintaining high-quality editorial standards for multilingual publications require significant investments in resources, including specialized personnel and technology.
- Ensuring consistency across languages in metadata and indexing poses a technical challenge that demands robust solutions.
- While DergiPark and TR Index provide substantial domestic support for multilingual publishing, enhancing their global presence and encouraging more journals to publish in widely spoken international languages like English remains a key objective.
- Developing partnerships with international indexing services to enhance the global visibility of multilingual works.
- Advocating for national policies that promote language diversity in academic publishing, supported by government and institutional funding.

In conclusion, TR Index and DergiPark exemplify Türkiye's commitment to promoting multilingualism in academic publishing. By integrating advanced technologies and

fostering collaborations, these platforms continue to enhance the inclusivity, accessibility, and global reach of Turkish scholarly outputs. As such, they play a vital role in shaping an open-access publishing environment that values both linguistic diversity and academic excellence.

5.3 Inclusivity and Accessibility

Language diversity plays a pivotal role in fostering inclusivity and accessibility within academic publishing. This section examines the influence of linguistic practices on the inclusivity of scholarly communication in Türkiye, highlighting the challenges encountered by non-English-speaking researchers and the strategies employed to support diverse linguistic communities.

In a country where Turkish serves as the primary language of education and communication, non-native English-speaking researchers often face significant obstacles when attempting to publish in internationally recognized journals that predominantly use English. Key challenges include limited proficiency in academic English, restricted access to professional language editing services, and the potential for misinterpretation of complex ideas due to linguistic barriers.

WCAG (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines) ensures digital content is accessible to everyone, including people with disabilities. To promote accessibility, platforms like DergiPark offer screen reader compatibility, adjustable text sizes, and high-contrast display options, making academic content inclusive for visually impaired users.

Based on four principles:

- *Perceivable*: Content must be detectable (e.g., alt text, captions, sufficient contrast).
- *Operable*: Interfaces must work with keyboards and avoid seizure triggers.
- *Understandable*: Content should be clear, predictable, and error-friendly.
- *Robust*: Compatible with assistive technologies and well-coded.

WCAG levels include A (basic), AA (common standard), and AAA (highest). DergiPark aims to achieve AA compliance by 2026, fostering an equitable publishing environment for all.

5.4 Impact of Language Diversity on Scholarly Communication

The language of academic publications significantly shapes the reach, citation potential, and overall impact of scholarly work. This section focuses on key aspects of linguistic diversity in scholarly communication, including inclusion in international indexing databases, opportunities for global academic collaboration, and the visibility of Turkish research within the global academic landscape. By addressing these concrete dimensions, the discussion seeks to highlight the essential role of language in shaping access to and recognition within the international research environment.

In Türkiye, citation metrics for journals, articles, and authors indexed in TR Index are routinely calculated. However, publications listed in international databases are often given greater weight in performance evaluations and have a stronger influence on global research impact. Consequently, the predominance of English as the lingua franca of scholarly communication has led to its increased usage, while the citation impact of Turkish-language publications remains comparatively low. These dynamics highlight the need for strategies to enhance the global visibility and accessibility of research conducted in Türkiye.

5.5 Supporting Language Diversity

Advancing language diversity in academic publishing necessitates coordinated efforts from publishers, academic institutions, policymakers, and the broader scholarly community. This section highlights initiatives and recommendations aimed at fostering language diversity within Turkish Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing. Key strategies include the development of comprehensive language support services, establishing partnerships for translation and editing, and advocating for the recognition and value of multilingual research outputs.

Currently, 72% of the articles hosted on the DergiPark platform are published in Turkish, 24% in English, and 4% in other languages such as German, French, Arabic, Russian,

Kurdish, and Azerbaijani. These figures underscore the importance of initiatives that support linguistic inclusivity and ensure that research across diverse languages gains visibility and recognition within the global academic community.

Conclusion

While there is currently no explicit policy addressing language diversity in Türkiye, the notion that Turkish publications are inherently less valuable than those published in English is misguided. Nevertheless, challenges related to international visibility may hinder the broader dissemination of these publications, limiting their potential impact. This limitation may prevent academic works in Turkish and other languages from receiving the recognition they deserve within the global scientific community.

Türkiye should work towards fostering a more inclusive academic environment by addressing language and accessibility barriers. Supporting the contributions of researchers from diverse linguistic backgrounds will enrich academic discourse and promote greater diversity in scholarly output. Such approaches will not only enhance the global scientific community but will also contribute to the creation of a more just and equitable academic publishing ecosystem, both locally and internationally.

Overcoming language barriers will not only enhance the visibility of local academic contributions but will also solidify Türkiye's scientific heritage on the global stage. Therefore, implementing strategic initiatives that support multilingualism in academic publishing is crucial for advancing both national and international academic collaboration and knowledge exchange.

6. Engagement and Best Practices

This section explores the role of Turkish Institutional Publishers and Service Providers (IPSPs) in engaging with the global academic and publishing communities to promote and advance best practices in Open Access (OA) publishing. It underscores the collaborative efforts of IPSPs, their adherence to international standards, and their initiatives aimed at improving the quality and ethical standards of scholarly communication.

One of the key efforts made by TR Index to enhance the quality of publishing involves a comprehensive approach that includes training programs and the publication of educational resources. In addition to the core processes and criteria established by TR Index, various events are organized for authors, researchers, editors, and referees to improve their understanding and engagement with scholarly publishing practices. Presentations and videos from these events are accessible online at TR Index Event Page, ensuring wider accessibility and dissemination of knowledge. Furthermore, TR Index has translated and made available crucial ethical guidelines, including the 'TR Index Ethical Principles Scheme' and the 'Editor's Handbook,' which can be accessed at TR Index Ethical Resources. These initiatives are critical in fostering a culture of ethical publishing in Türkiye.

Since 2012, Türkiye has celebrated Open Access Week annually, a significant event aimed at raising awareness about open access and its related issues. This week serves as a platform for researchers, publishers, librarians, and funders to come together and engage in discussions about the challenges and opportunities within the open access ecosystem. Alongside Open Access Week, Türkiye regularly organizes various events and activities to promote open access, further contributing to the global movement towards making research freely accessible to all. These events provide valuable opportunities for the academic community to stay informed and share insights on the evolving landscape of open access publishing.

Furthermore, developments in open access are shared and discussed during the ANKOS (The Turkish Academic Network and Information Centre) annual meetings. These

meetings are attended by representatives from university libraries across Türkiye, bringing together researchers, publishers, librarians, and funders to engage in dialogue and exchange knowledge on best practices in open access publishing.

Another key event where open access issues are highlighted is Library Week, organized by the Turkish Librarians Association (TKD) every March since 1964. This long-standing tradition serves as an important occasion for professionals in the library and information science field to reflect on and promote the importance of open access and scholarly communication.

Additionally, in 2016, Türkiye established the Creative Commons (CC) Türkiye Team, which has since enabled the country to actively participate in the global Creative Commons organization. The CC Türkiye Team organizes regular community meetings, training sessions, and webinars to educate and engage local stakeholders in the principles of open access and the benefits of using open licensing to share knowledge. Through these initiatives, Türkiye continues to make significant strides in advancing open access and supporting a more inclusive, accessible academic publishing landscape.

6.1 Community Engagement and Collaboration

Engagement with academic communities, both at the local and global levels, is essential for the growth and continued improvement of Open Access (OA) publishing. This subsection explores the efforts made by Turkish Institutional Publishers and Service Providers (IPSPs) to foster community engagement through collaborations, consortia, and networks. It highlights the importance of partnerships in enhancing resource sharing, building capacity, and advocating collectively for OA initiatives.

One notable example of community-driven engagement is the Aperta Platform, which plays a central role in bringing together various academic groups and research communities across different subject areas. By organizing these groups under specific thematic communities, Aperta facilitates collaboration and knowledge sharing, making

it easier for researchers and institutions to access relevant publications and data. The platform serves as a hub for these communities, promoting both academic networking and the dissemination of scholarly content. Publications and data from these communities can be accessed through the Aperta platform at Aperta Communities, further strengthening the accessibility and visibility of academic outputs within Türkiye and beyond.

Through such platforms and initiatives, Turkish IPSPs are contributing to the creation of a more integrated and collaborative academic environment, where resources, expertise, and support can be shared to advance the goals of Open Access publishing.

6.2 Adherence to International Publishing Standards

Maintaining international standards is essential for ensuring the quality, transparency, and credibility of academic publications. This section examines the extent to which Turkish Institutional Publishers and Service Providers (IPSPs) adhere to established international publishing standards, including those set by the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE), and the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). It also addresses the challenges IPSPs face in aligning with these standards and outlines strategies for overcoming them.

To ensure ethical assurance in scientific periodical publishing, TR Index has adopted key guidelines, such as the "Code of Conduct and Best Practice Guidelines for Journal Editors" and the "Code of Conduct for Journal Publishers" established by COPE. These guidelines serve as foundational principles for upholding high standards in scholarly publishing. In alignment with TR Index's criteria, journals are required to comply with COPE and other international publishing standards. Moreover, editors are tasked with ensuring that each research output receives approval from relevant boards and commissions before publication. As stipulated in the TR Index Evaluation Criteria, adherence to both international publishing and ethical standards is a fundamental requirement.

To further support compliance with these standards, TR Index organizes training sessions focused on publishing principles, ethical considerations, editing, and peer reviewing. These sessions are designed to raise awareness and provide practical guidance to researchers and editors. Additionally, TR Index has developed an Ethical Principles chart, which is available on its website to further facilitate the understanding and implementation of these guidelines. The chart can be accessed at TR Index Ethical Principles.

Reaching a wide audience is of utmost importance for TÜBİTAK's academic journals; however, this is pursued with a strong commitment to ethical publishing and adherence to established academic standards. As part of this goal, preparations have begun for the development of a dedicated application, which is planned to be completed by July 2025. In parallel, existing journal policies are being reviewed, and new policies are being drafted—particularly to address emerging developments such as the use of artificial intelligence in academic publishing. As part of this process, the publication policies of these journals have been revised to align with the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license, ensuring wider accessibility and compliance with global open access standards. This initiative exemplifies the ongoing efforts of TÜBİTAK Academic Journals and TR Index to set benchmarks for scholarly publishing in Türkiye. It is anticipated that the adoption of the CC BY 4.0 license and inclusion in the DOAJ will increase across the country in the near future.

Furthermore, the European Association of Science Editors (EASE) represents a global community of editors who come from diverse linguistic and professional backgrounds and share a commitment to advancing science, scholarly communication, and publishing. As part of its international engagement, ULAKBİM, along with its staff and some of its reviewers, is actively involved in EASE and participates in events aimed at fostering the development of national scientific publishing and strengthening international cooperation in the field. Through such collaborations, Türkiye continues to contribute to the advancement of global scholarly communication and the enhancement of ethical publishing practices.

6.3 Best Practices in Editorial and Peer Review Processes

This section explores how Turkish Institutional Publishers and Service Providers (IPSPs) contribute to upholding and advancing best practices in Open Access (OA) publishing, particularly in terms of editorial and peer review processes. By examining their collaborative efforts, adherence to international standards, and initiatives aimed at improving the quality and ethical integrity of scholarly communication, this section highlights the vital role these practices play in enhancing the academic publishing landscape.

At the core of the academic publishing model lies the integrity of the editorial process and peer review system. Turkish academic publishers, through their editorial policies and peer review practices, strive to ensure fairness, transparency, and rigor in their operations. Adherence to best practices is ensured through well-established guidelines, rigorous ethical review processes, and continuous training initiatives. As stipulated in the TR Index Journal Evaluation Criteria, journals are expected to comply with scientific and ethical publishing principles. Journals that fail to meet these criteria are removed from the index, ensuring that only those adhering to high standards are promoted.

To maintain the integrity of editorial and peer review processes, TÜBİTAK Academic Journals have developed comprehensive guidelines and created standardized evaluation forms for referees. These forms ensure that articles undergo a consistent and thorough evaluation, addressing fundamental questions of scientific rigor and ethical considerations. Additionally, TÜBİTAK places a strong emphasis on forming international and gender-balanced editorial boards, ensuring objectivity and fostering diversity in academic publishing decisions. These efforts are critical not only for maintaining high standards in academic publishing at the national level but also for elevating Türkiye's academic visibility in the international arena.

In a rapidly globalizing academic world, Turkish academic publishers continue to undertake improvement initiatives aligned with internationalization goals. These efforts contribute significantly to the recognition of local academic values worldwide and support the advancement of scientific diversity.

6.4 Open Science and Data Sharing

Open Science principles extend beyond open access publications, encompassing open data, open methodology, and public engagement in research. This section examines how Turkish IPSPs incorporate Open Science practices into their operations, focusing on data-sharing policies, reproducibility standards, and public engagement initiatives. These practices are critical for fostering greater transparency, collaboration, and accessibility in research.

In 2018, the APERTA Türkiye Open Archive was established as an open data repository for TÜBİTAK-funded research, project publications, corporate publications, and related research data. The platform, built on the open-source Invenio RDM (Research Data Management) software, was expanded in 2020 to become the Turkish Open Archive, serving as a national open archive. Open to all researchers in Türkiye, Aperta provides Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for datasets at no cost, facilitating better discoverability and citation of research data. Researchers can access the project at Aperta.

The TÜBİTAK Open Science Policy further supports the integration of Open Science principles by mandating the storage of accepted-for-publication peer-reviewed articles in the TÜBİTAK Open Archive. This requirement ensures that all metadata is fully open, scannable, and machine-readable from the moment of storage. Additionally, the Open Science policy aligns with the FAIR principles – Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability – ensuring that research data is not only accessible but also usable and reusable for future research. By adhering to these principles, Aperta ensures the long-term preservation, management, and free access to research data, reaching 5.746 datasets to date.

6.5 Capacity Building and Professional Development

Building capacity in scholarly publishing is essential for ensuring the sustainable growth of OA publishing. This subsection highlights the professional development and training opportunities provided by Turkish IPSPs to enhance the skills of researchers, editors,

and publishers. These training initiatives focus on topics such as publishing best practices, ethical considerations, and the principles of Open Science.

Through these capacity-building efforts, Turkish IPSPs contribute significantly to the quality and effectiveness of OA publishing in Türkiye. The training programs aim to foster a deeper understanding of academic publishing standards and ethical guidelines, ensuring that stakeholders are equipped with the necessary tools and knowledge to engage effectively in scholarly communication. By supporting the professional development of individuals in the academic publishing ecosystem, these initiatives help to strengthen the overall quality and sustainability of OA publishing practices in the country.

Conclusion

This section comprehensively explores how Turkish Institutional Publishers and Service Providers (IPSPs) engage with both local and global academic communities to advance Open Access (OA) publishing. By focusing on collaborative efforts, adherence to international standards, and initiatives aimed at enhancing the quality and ethical integrity of scholarly communication, this report highlights the critical role Turkish IPSPs play in shaping the evolving landscape of academic publishing.

Since 2012, Türkiye has marked the annual celebration of Open Access Week, a significant initiative aimed at raising awareness about open access and its associated issues. This event serves as a platform for discussions on the future of academic publishing, bringing together researchers, publishers, librarians, and funders from various sectors. In addition to Open Access Week, a wide range of periodic events and activities are organized to stimulate dialogue and promote best practices in OA publishing. Among these, the ANKOS annual meetings play a key role in discussing developments in open access, with university library representatives and other stakeholders contributing to the conversation. Similarly, Library Week, organized annually by the Turkish Librarians Association (TKD) since 1964, continues to be an essential occasion for discussing scholarly publishing issues, including open access.

Furthermore, the Creative Commons (CC) Türkiye Team, formed in 2016, has been instrumental in promoting open access and fostering community engagement. By organizing community meetings, training sessions, and webinars, the team has significantly contributed to enhancing understanding of open access principles, providing Turkish researchers and publishers with the tools and knowledge needed to engage with the global OA movement.

The adherence to international standards is paramount for maintaining the quality, transparency, and credibility of academic publications. Turkish IPSPs demonstrate their commitment to upholding these standards by aligning with organizations such as the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE), and the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). These standards ensure that Turkish scholarly publications meet the highest ethical and scientific benchmarks. However, aligning with these standards does not come without challenges. This report discusses the obstacles faced by Turkish publishers in meeting these standards and the strategies they have adopted to overcome them. For example, the TR Index, a key national publication index, follows COPE's guidelines to guarantee ethical publishing practices, and training sessions on publishing principles are regularly conducted to raise awareness and improve compliance.

In line with international standards, TÜBİTAK Academic Journals plans to apply for inclusion in DOAJ for all of its 11 publications in July 2025. This move is part of a broader strategy to align with the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) license, further emphasizing transparency and accessibility in scholarly publishing. TÜBİTAK has also developed comprehensive editorial guidelines, along with standardized evaluation forms for reviewers, ensuring that manuscripts are subjected to consistent and rigorous peer review. These measures aim to enhance the fairness, transparency, and overall quality of the editorial process, which is a core tenet of successful academic publishing.

The principles of Open Science, which extend beyond the mere accessibility of publications to include open data, open methodology, and public engagement in research, have also been integrated into the practices of Turkish IPSPs. A key initiative

in this regard is the APERTA Türkiye Open Archive, launched in 2018 as an open data repository for research outputs funded by TÜBİTAK. APERTA serves as a national open archive and provides free access to research data, supporting the principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR). By offering long-term storage, preservation, and management of research data, APERTA facilitates the reuse and broader dissemination of valuable research findings. This repository has grown significantly, with over 71,000 articles, over 5,746 datasets currently available, demonstrating Türkiye's commitment to advancing Open Science practices at both the national and international levels.

In conclusion, the ongoing efforts of Turkish IPSPs to foster collaboration, maintain high editorial standards, and integrate Open Science principles underscore the country's active role in the global transition to Open Access. The initiatives discussed in this report, including the promotion of open access awareness, the adoption of international publishing standards, and the development of open data repositories, collectively contribute to enhancing the visibility, quality, and ethical standards of Turkish academic publishing. As these efforts continue to evolve, they not only support the growth of OA publishing in Türkiye but also contribute to the global movement towards more accessible, transparent, and inclusive scholarly communication.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

DIAMAS Türkiye Country Report highlights the significant strides Türkiye has made in the realm of Diamond Open Access (OA) publishing, underscoring the active involvement of higher education institutions, the diversification of funding sources, and the strategic adoption of open access policies. These developments reflect a promising trajectory for the country's academic publishing landscape, with efforts from institutions like TÜBİTAK ULAKBİM playing a pivotal role in advancing the open access agenda. Despite the progress, several challenges remain, particularly around funding sustainability, technological disparities, and the need for strengthened international collaborations. Addressing these issues will be crucial for Türkiye to maximize the potential benefits of open access publishing, ensuring long-term sustainability and global impact.

The rapid development of OA in Türkiye has been driven by global trends, regional initiatives, and national policies aimed at enhancing the visibility and accessibility of Turkish research. A key milestone in this effort was the letter sent by the Council of Higher Education (YÖK) in 2019, requesting universities to establish Open Archives and appoint Rectors or Vice-Rectors responsible for open science initiatives. This initiative has since led to the creation of the YÖK Open Academic Archive System, which operates according to international standards. 3,903,128 records from the open archives of 174 universities is periodically integrated into this system as part of the Harman project, led by ULAKBİM.

The establishment of institutional and national policies that align with international standards is essential for the success of Open Science in Türkiye. Open access not only facilitates the wider dissemination of research but also enhances its societal impact by ensuring that scientific results are easily accessible to a broader audience. TÜBİTAK has been a pioneer in Türkiye's OA movement, signing agreements with major publishers such as Wiley and Springer, enabling Turkish researchers to publish open access articles. Additionally, Türkiye's participation in international OA initiatives like the SCOAP3 consortium further amplifies the country's engagement with global open access efforts.

TÜBİTAK's commitment to open access is evident in its recent mandate for all publications resulting from its funded projects to be made open access. The institution has also developed policies to ensure compliance with these requirements, aiming to align Türkiye's research output with international OA practices. Furthermore, TÜBİTAK has been at the forefront of supporting Diamond Open Access through its ULAKBİM platform, which hosts local and regional journals as part of the DergiPark project—an exemplary service for Diamond Open Access publishing. The signing of the "Action Plan for Diamond Open Access" in 2022 marks a significant step toward further institutionalizing OA publishing in Türkiye.

The findings from this report underscore Türkiye's commitment to expanding and enhancing OA publishing, with a growing adoption of international best practices and increasing involvement from higher education institutions, governmental bodies, and global publishing standards. The active engagement of Turkish researchers, publishers, and institutions in OA initiatives demonstrates the country's progressive stance within the global academic community. However, challenges related to sustainable funding, technological infrastructure, language diversity, and international visibility must be addressed to fully realize the potential of open access publishing in Türkiye. Overcoming these barriers will be essential to ensure broader dissemination of research, stronger academic collaboration, and increased public engagement with scholarly work.

Recommendations

Based on the analysis presented in this report, the following recommendations are proposed to stakeholders in the Turkish Diamond OA ecosystem:

1. **Strengthen Funding Models:** Develop diversified and sustainable funding models to ensure the long-term viability of OA publishing. This includes exploring avenues for governmental support, institutional funding, and international grants. Given the importance of stable financial backing for sustaining OA platforms and initiatives, diversified funding streams are essential for the future growth of OA publishing in Türkiye.
2. **Enhance Technological Infrastructure:** Invest in advanced publishing technologies and platforms that streamline editorial processes, improve accessibility, and ensure compliance with international standards. The development of sophisticated technological infrastructure will not only enhance the efficiency of the publishing process but also help Turkish OA platforms maintain high editorial and production standards, aligning with global best practices.
3. **Promote Language Diversity:** Encourage multilingual publishing to reflect Türkiye's linguistic diversity and enhance the global reach and impact of Turkish research. Supporting services such as translations and linguistic editing will improve the accessibility and inclusivity of Turkish scholarly outputs, enabling research to reach broader international audiences and making it more relevant in diverse academic contexts.
4. **Foster International Collaboration:** Strengthen partnerships with international publishers, scholarly societies, and OA initiatives to share knowledge, resources, and best practices. Türkiye's active participation in global OA networks will increase the visibility of Turkish research, contribute to the global knowledge economy, and ensure that Turkish researchers are included in important international academic discussions.
5. **Invest in Capacity Building:** Provide training and professional development opportunities for researchers, editors, and publishers to improve the quality of

OA publications and promote ethical and transparent publishing practices. This will help build the necessary expertise within Türkiye's academic community, ensuring that OA publications adhere to high editorial standards and ethical guidelines.

6. **Advocate for Open Science Practices:** Encourage the broader adoption of Open Science principles, including open data, open peer review, and public engagement with research. Supporting policies and infrastructure that promote Open Science will help increase the transparency, reproducibility, and credibility of Turkish research. This can also facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration and accelerate the pace of scientific discovery.
7. **Monitor and Evaluate Progress:** Implement mechanisms for regularly monitoring and evaluating OA initiatives and policies. By gathering feedback and analysing data-driven insights, Türkiye can ensure continuous improvement and adaptability in response to the evolving academic and publishing landscapes. Regular evaluations will also help identify areas for enhancement and ensure the effectiveness of OA strategies.

Final Words

As Türkiye continues to navigate the rapidly evolving landscape of academic publishing, its commitment to open access and the principles of inclusivity, transparency, and collaboration will be crucial in securing a leading position in the global academic community. By addressing the challenges outlined in this report and embracing the recommended strategies, Türkiye can further strengthen its contribution to the global knowledge economy. This will ensure that Turkish research remains accessible, impactful, and enduring, fostering academic growth, collaboration, and the wider dissemination of scientific knowledge.

Appendices

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List of Tables

Table 1 Language distribution of articles in DergiPark	11
Table 2 Number of journals in TR Index according to publication language	41

List of figures

Figure 1 Distribution of universities based on the number of journals they publish	13
Figure 2 Number of hybrid and gold open access articles affiliated with institutions in Türkiye and published by Wiley from 2022 to 2024	14
Figure 3 Number of open access articles from institutions in Türkiye published in Springer hybrid journals (2020-2024)	15
Figure 4 Annual distribution of publications indexed in TR Dizin by access type (2014-2024)	26
Figure 5 Annual number of journals indexed in DergiPark (2013-2024)	31
Figure 6 Annual number of articles displayed in DergiPark (2014-2024)	32
Figure 7 Annual number of registered users on DergiPark (2014-2024)	33
Figure 8 Browser language preferences of DergiPark users based on Google Analytics data (January-December 2024)	35
Figure 9 Language distribution of published articles in DergiPark	38

